

ESTABLISHING PEER-COUNSELING THROUGH PEER INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION IN THE SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract:

Student problems at school are often being a hot topic that never ends in the school environment. 70% of the average student in school ever had problems, including, family problems, social conflict, behavioral deviations, economic problems, difficulties in understanding lessons, health problems, pressure from others and problems of self-competence and self-confidence. The results of interviews with school counselors, showed a significant decrease in academic achievement with an increase in cases that occurred or experienced by students at school. Teachers, school principals and school counselors are always required to immediately resolve problems that occur to students as soon as possible without having risks that an impact on the negative image of the institution / school and damage the performance imagery that has been obtained by the institution with great struggle and hard work. To maintain the achievement, the school will impose sanctions on students who violate school rules or commit uncommon breaking norm in school or outside school with various punishments to them. On the other hand, providing rewards / prizes for those who have great achievement in academics and non-academics to make the institution / name of the school became famous and outstanding. The results of the study the influence of peer interpersonal communication on increasing student academic success is quite high in some high schools in the Pontianak city by 77% of the total 264 respondents. Various efforts to prevent and resolve student problems are carried out by school counselors in handling various cases that occur in the school environment through observation, dialogue and long discussions with counselors in the school. Researchers traced cases that occurred at schools in Pontianak and studied counseling guidance programs implemented at schools in helping educational institutions / schools guide, direct and assist students in

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overcoming various problems that they faced. Through peer counseling activities and optimizing peer interpersonal communication in the student environment at school. The researcher conducted a survey of several schools in Pontianak, including High School, Vocational High School and Madrasah Aliyah (Islamic high school), by conducting observations and interviews with students and school counselors on the formation of peer-counseling in the school environment through interpersonal peer communication that exists in teaching and learning process activities and non-academic activities in schools.

Keywords: peer-counseling, peer interpersonal communication, school environment

1. Introduction

Several previous studies showed that more than half (54.3%) the role of active peers in providing information about reproductive health. There is a relationship between the role of positive peers with premarital sexual behavior, where respondents with passive peers are 2.6 times more likely to engage in premarital sexual behavior than respondents with active peers. The existence of friends is one of the five things that most concern teenagers, namely as friends, as people who want to listen, want to help, and can communicate deeply, and even can be a helpful angel. These are the mindset of several teenagers in high school.

Various efforts to prevent and resolve student problems are carried out by school counselors in handling various cases that occur in the school environment. Through observation, dialogue and long discussions with the counselors in the school, the researcher traced the cases that occurred in schools in the Pontianak and studied counseling guidance programs implemented in schools. These efforts to help students to overcome various problems that they faced through peer counseling activities by optimizing peer-to-peer interpersonal communication in the student environment at school.

The researcher has conducted a survey of several schools in Pontianak, including High School, Vocational High School and Madrasah Aliyah, by observing and interviewing students and school counselors on the formation of peer-counseling in the school environment. Through interpersonal communication peers who are involved in teaching and learning process activities and non-academic activities in schools. With the 120 students who gave statements, 84 preferred peer counseling than counselor teachers or 70% stated that it was easier and more convenient to communicate with peers in raising problems and resolving all problems and discussing appropriate solutions in overcoming the problems they had natural.

The intimate relationship between each other is built through peer-to-peer interpersonal communication that allows each other to help each other in unique ways. The counselee will feel more emotional intimate with peer counselors when compared with expert counselors (counselor teacher / guidance counselor teacher). Thus, the atmosphere of counseling becomes more pleasant. Peer counseling is seen as important

because based on the researcher's observations most teenagers more often discuss their problems with peers compared to parents, mentors, or teachers at school (Sujiwo, (2008) in the National Seminar on Guidance and Counseling 12-13 March 2008 - UPI). In addition Tindall and Gray (1985) define peer guidance as a variety of individual behaviors that seek to help other individuals interpersonal. These relationships can be done individually (one-to-one helping relationship) or in the form of group leadership, discussion leadership, or peer interpersonal activities aimed at helping or helping students, from various negative influences and in dealing with various problems that occur in teenage life.

Teenagers are the next generation of the nation who are expected to be able to replace the previous generations with better quality of performance and mentality. Especially in facing the current global era, the readiness of adolescents as part of potential human resources is expected to play a role in developing Indonesia's nation in order to compete with other nations in the world. Adolescents in their role as the next generation of the nation are expected to have good performance and mental qualities, as the capital needed to become a nation leader.

Laurence M. Bramer (in Lobby Loekmono, 1985), she revealed that many people tend to prefer to raise issues through sharing or sharing with their close friends/ peers than to teachers or parents. Rosmala Dewi's research results: 2013, the needs of students for peer counselors have an average of 90.17 that's mean the needs of students for peer counselors are characterized by a high category. Shertzer & Stone (1981) states that peer groups, Laursen (2005: 138) states that positive peer groups enable adolescents to feel being accepted, can be used as a substitute for family, functioning to stabilize influence during the transition period, through dialogue / interpersonal communication peers among teenagers

2. The Importance of Peer-Counseling that is Being Established at Schools

In its development, a teenager cannot be separated from other social groups, such as peer groups. This environment / group will determine the individual's growth, as revealed by Hamachek (in Shertzer & Stone, 1981), that the peer group can be used as a substitute for the family, during the transition period, gaining self-confidence and protection from adult abuse. Syamsu Yusuf, 2009, stated that peer tutoring is guidance conducted by students towards other students. Students who have been mentors before given training or coaching by the counselor. Based on the opinion above, it can be concluded that peer guidance is a process of guidance and counseling services conducted by students (who have been given training and coaching by counselors) towards other students in order to solve the problem.

For the implementation of peer counseling at school, peer counselor must have interpersonal communication skills. Service and counseling programs will not succeed effectively without the active assistance of students (peers) in solving developmental crises and psychological problems that occur and experienced. Counselors must engage students (peers help other students solve problems rationally and logically. Research

Results on the Effectiveness of Peer Counseling Carr, (1981: 2) and Judy A. Tindall & Dean Gray, (1985: 24) show that most services which was given through peer counseling was successful.

Emmert (1977) found that groups of students who had received training became peer-helper get higher score in empathy than groups of students who did not receive training. Suwarjo (2008) has proven that the peer counseling model is effective in developing the attitude of resilience of foster children of the Children Orphanage at Yogyakarta Special province. In the UK "peer counseling" has a very strong role, providing legal protection for the development of education, environment, family, etc. "Peer counseling" becomes a mediation for prevention and overcoming various conflicts between groups.

Burley S, Gutkin T and Naumann W, (1994) stated: "*Peer tutoring is shown to be successful and is used as a strategy for mainstream children.*" Dolan, B. (1994). Found: "*A teen talk line run by peers is shown to be effective and has an impact on the self-esteem of peers.*" Heppner, P. P. and Johnston, J. A., (1994) stated, Specific steps are implemented to implement a peer consultation program and evidence about its success is provided along with suggestions for modifications. Almasi, J. F. (1994) stated in their writings, Students in peer-led groups sexed themselves more fully and explored topics that are interested in them and are recognized and resolved conflicts better than students in teacher-led groups.

3. Effect of Peer Interpersonal Communication on Students' Academic Success

Peer interpersonal communication is interpersonal communication among students of the same age as peers approaching the same age, to provide information, attention and calmness when they experienced difficulties, pressures and problems, Cowie and Wallace, (2000). Peer interpersonal communication is very influential on academic success and their teenage lives, giving confidence, giving advice and guidance when students experienced difficulties, pressures and problems.

The communication relationship is based on:

3.1 Mutual Trust

The trust factor is the most important factor in determining the effectiveness of interpersonal communication. Trust to others is to improve interpersonal communication, because it opens communication channels, communicant opportunities to achieve their goals (Winfield, 1994).

3.2 Positive Social Interaction when Adversity Problems or Situations

Students have adversity problem that occur in school and tend to solve by themselves. Counselor should have positive social interaction. One of the solutions is through interactions and interpersonal communication that occurs between peers, either through spontaneous unstructured interactions, or through programmed interactions. DeVito (Fajar, 2009).

3.3. Emotional Control

Teenagers also need attention and comfort when they face problems, need people who are willing to listen sympathetically, seriously, and provide opportunities to share difficulties and feelings such as anger, fear, anxiety, and doubt (Cowie and Wallace, 2000).

Based on the results of the study, the influence of peer interpersonal communication on increasing student academic success is quite high in several high schools / high schools in Pontianak, by 77% of the 264 respondents.

Criteria	Interval	F	%
Low	<18.67	0	0%
Average	18.67-29.32	204	77%
High	>=29.33	60	23%

The high influence of peer interpersonal communication in increasing students' academic success at school, provides an overview of communication that exists in the peer environment, especially in schools that has a positive impact on the learning process at school. They give each other information and guidance to other friends who have difficulty in learning or problems that are being faced through social interaction that occurs between them. Peer interpersonal communication, is a reciprocal relationship between students whose age is approaching the same in oral form, occurs in every activity and process of activities in students' lives that affect the improvement of learning outcomes or academic success.

4. Establishing of Peer-Counseling through Peer-to-Peer Communication in the School

Peers is a very influential factor on life in the teen years P. Laursen (2005: 137) and this fact is seen from the lives of adolescents in modern society as it is now spending most of their time together with their peers (Steinberg, 1993: 154). The formation of peer counselors / peer counseling begins with the communication that occurs between peers in positive interactions that take place intensively. Such communication develops spontaneously and mutual trust through the modeling process. They can transmit, imitate and internalize certain attitudes, skills, and various strategies among them that appear from peer counselors. Besides that, peer counselors can also directly teach resilience skills to peers when they share about an issue. Through such vehicles and methods, peer resilience will increase (Winfield (1994: 3)).

Children's development is greatly influenced by what happens in other social contexts such as relationships with peers. All interpersonal activities of peers are carried out to help or help students acting as a guide that is a reciprocal relationship characterized by two-way communication; attention to verbal and non-verbal aspects, the use of questions to explore information, feelings and thoughts, and effective

listening attitudes. According to Carr (1981), there are several considerations that underlie the importance of peer counseling, namely:

- 1) students make their friends as the first source in considering making personal decisions,
- 2) various skills related to effective assistance can be learned even by common ordinary people,
- 3) students need to have competence, i.e. tend to be strong, need intelligence, i.e. can understand the atmosphere, and take on the role of responsibility to be respectable and self-esteem, i.e. to be meaningful and understandable,
- 4) studies conducted by Pallen (1976: 134) show that the use of peers can improve the achievement and self-esteem of other students,
- 5) the need for peers is one of the five things that most concern children and adolescents.

5. Procedure for Implementing "Peer Counseling"

Peers are children or adolescents with the same age / maturity level. Furthermore Santrock (2002: 44) states that peers or peers are children with the same level of maturity or age. Carr (1981: 3) stated "*basically peer counseling is a way for students to learn how to care about others and put their caring into practice*". Basically, peer counseling is a way for students (teenagers) to learn how to pay attention and help other children, and apply it in their daily lives. In the formation of peer counseling in adolescents, the steps that can be taken, said by Suwarjo (2008: 12) there are 3 stages namely selecting prospective peer counselors, providing training, and organizing the implementation of peer counseling. The following four stages will be explained:

5.1 Selection of Prospective Peer Counseling

Selection is based on good and warm characteristics, has an interest in helping each other, can be acceptable to others, tolerant to differences in value systems, energetic, being voluntarily and willing to help others, has stable emotions, and has sufficient learning achievement at good or minimum average score, and be able to keep a secret. In each class 3 or 4 students can be selected who eligible to these criteria.

5.2 Peer Counseling Training

The main purpose of peer counselor training is to increase the number of young people who have and are able to use aid-giving skills. This training is not intended to produce a person who replaces the function and role of the counselor.

5.3 Implementation and Organization of Peer Counseling.

In practice, the interaction of "counseling" peers is more spontaneous and informal. Spontaneous means that the interaction can occur anytime and anywhere.

Judy A. Tindall & H. Dean Gray (1985) argued: "*peer counseling is defined as a variety of interpersonal helping behaviors that have been assisted by non-professionals who use*

roles with others" explained that: "*peer counseling includes one-to-one helping relationships, group leadership, discussion leadership, advice, tutoring helping or assisting nature*". Peer counseling includes one-to-one helping relationships, group leadership, discussion leadership, consideration giving, tutorials, and all interpersonal activities. Peer counseling should be a nonprofessional counselor for his friends.

Prospective peer-counselor students will get a series of adequate training to become peer counselors, so that it is expected to improve the ability of students (who are trained as peer-counselors and counsees who are mentored) in dealing with problems. Basics of communication skills that need to be trained in "Peer Counselors" Judy A. Tindall & H. Dean Gray (1985), from the counseling training format from Carkhuff (1969), Ivey (1973), Gordon (1970), fundamentals of communication skills which need to be trained on "Peer Counselor" or to non-professional staff. As in the following table:

Table 2: Format of Peer Counseling Training, Carkhuff, 1969, Gordon 1970

No.	Communication Skill	Technique	Categorization
1	Acceptance	Used to show interest, understanding of the things expressed counselee	Verbal communication
2.	Attending	Giving respect / full attention to counselee	Verbal / Non verbal communication
3.	Summarizing	Summarizing what has been stated by the counselee	Verbal communication
4.	Questioning	Exploring counsees or provide answers to counselee desires that are deep meaning	Verbal communication
5.	Genuineness	Honestly communicates feelings	Verbal communication
6.	Assertiveness	Expressing thoughts and feelings honestly, by being straightforward	Verbal communication
7.	Confrontation	Expressing gaps in counselee behavior	Verbal / Non verbal communication
8.	Problem Solving	Evaluates behaviors that affect the resolution of counselee's problem	Verbal communication

Peer counseling training is a deliberate, systematic and structured form of psychological education. Through peer counseling allows students to have the skills to implement the experience of independence and the ability to control themselves which is very meaningful for adolescents. Peer counseling programs can be done in class, workshop or training seminars. To find out the success of the program carried out in peer-counseling can be evaluated, as part of the training and peer-counseling program to measure the progress and integrated problems of the whole program

Peer counseling is seen as important because most adolescents (students and students) discuss their problems more often with peers than parents, mentors, or teachers at school. For problems that are considered very serious even they discuss with peers (friends). Even if there are teenagers who end up telling their serious problems to

parents, mentors or teachers, it is usually because they have been forced (conversations and problem-solving efforts with peers experience a dead end).

In such conditions the treatment of parents often scolds them and cannot accept those who are involved in delinquency cases at school and experience failure in learning or seeing their learning outcomes are low or fail to get upper class. Teachers and school counselors said they lacked guidance and direction and helped them intensively.

The results of Buhrmester's study were strengthened and supported by the findings of Nickerson & Nagle (2005: 240) that in adolescence communication and trust in parents diminished and turned to peers to meet the need for attachment. Meanwhile, alcoholic teenagers do not have a good relationship with their peers and have difficulty in building trust in others, Muro & Kottman (1995: 229). Teenagers need affection from other teenagers, and need respectful physical contact. Teenagers also need attention and comfort when they face problems, need people who are willing to listen sympathetically, seriously, and provide opportunities to share difficulties and feelings such as anger, fear, anxiety, and doubt (Cowie and Wallace, 2000).

Peers or peers are children with more or less the same level of maturity or age. One of the most important functions of peer groups is to provide sources of information and comparisons about the world outside the family. Through peer groups children receive feedback from their friends about their abilities. Positive peer behavioral habits help teens to understand that they are not alone in facing challenges (Santrock, 2004).

Peer counseling is seen as important because based on the researcher's observations are most teenagers more often discuss their problems with peers compared to parents, mentors, or teachers at school.

6. Conclusion

Based on the above discussion, several conclusions can be concluded: peer-counseling services have a big enough opportunity to be implemented in schools, if it is done by professional counselors and supported by various parties, especially school principals, and teachers. The positive interpersonal communication interactions of peers are a very appropriate approach to form peer counseling in schools, as an effort to help school parties overcome various student problems that occur between students. the steps for establishing peer-counseling appropriately can be done by providing counseling skills training to students, such as acceptance, attending, summarizing, questioning, genuineness, assertiveness, confrontation, and problem solving. A peer counselor should have good communication between peers, based on mutual trust, positive interaction and emotional control, to be able to control his emotions when there is unpleasant dialogue between peers.

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